

EFFECT OF BRAND NAME ON CONSUMER PREFERENCES FOR CHOCOLATE BEVERAGES IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This work examined the effect of brand name on consumer preferences for chocolate beverages in North Central states, Nigeria. Relevant conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study is anchored on brand loyalty correlate theory. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The target population for the study consists of 45,173 undergraduates students of federal universities across North Central States. A sample size of 396 was selected. Brand image, brand quality, brand awareness and brand association were employed as the independent variable while consumer preference was employed as the dependent variable. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics and ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique. Brand image, brand quality, brand awareness and brand association were found to have significant positive effect on undergraduates' preference. Based on the findings, the study concludes that brand name has significant positive effect on university undergraduates' preference. The study, therefore, recommends that organizations and marketers should use effective promotional tools to create strong brand awareness within customers' minds.

Key Words: Brand Name, Brand Image, Brand Quality, Brand Awareness and Brand Association, Consumer Preference.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the study of consumer behavior has attracted a lot of researchers' attention due to its dynamism and probably its relevance in the business world. Importantly, the closer interplay between theoretical and empirical considerations alongside rapid expansion in the availability of different types of data has continued to make the analysis of consumer behavior an attractive area for research. The dynamism of consumers seen from the point of view of university undergraduates in this study can be traced to the fact that humans act and behave differently at different times in the process of purchase. Aside from this, the consumer dynamism may be linked to the variations in

thinking, feelings, and actions of individuals, target consumer groups, and/or the larger society (Peter & Olson, 2008).

During the past two decades, it has become evident that brands are among a company's most important assets (Naufal, Muhammad & Mukhamad, 2016). Tooraj and Elham (2012) stated that the success of most powerful corporations in the world was largely based on their strong brands. A dichotomy can roughly be drawn between firms operating in developed and those in developing economies. Whereas the former are increasingly gravitating towards societal and sustainability marketing concept whose main focus are satisfying customer needs and wants using environmental methods, the latter seem to operate hugely either under the product and production concepts. Firms in those economies seem to produce goods and services with limited consideration of consumer needs, wants, and aspirations. Successful brands are known to create and articulate the sustainable differential advantages of the underlying products (Ward, 2004).

Importantly, Nigeria beverage industry seems to be witnessing a radical revolution culminating in huge increase in the production of local brands and heightened importation of foreign beverage brands which arguably create brand preference challenge to rapidly expanding millennium university undergraduates in the North-central Nigeria. For instance, companies such as Nestle, Cadbury, Promasidor, Glaxosmithkline among other locally-based manufacturers produce a lot of chocolate beverage brands with somewhat similar attributes that consumers evaluate based on individual vital criteria particularly when making purchase decisions among alternative chocolate beverage brands in the marketplace and/or market-space. The major chocolate beverage brands covered in this study include Bournvita from the production line of Cadbury Nigeria Plc, Milo, manufactured by Nestle Nigeria Plc, Ovaltine, produced by Twining Nigeria, Cowbell Choco, manufactured by Promasidor Nigeria Limited and Horlicks, produced by Glaxosmithkline Consumer Plc. The rapidly increasing beverage brands appear to have engendered intense competition and facilitated consumer, especially university undergraduates, mobility in terms of preference. Manufacturers appear increasingly compelled to pull more innovative combination of tricks out of the bag to attract consumers towards various brands of chocolate beverages. Increasingly, regulatory agencies are intensifying campaign on the order-qualifying-attributes of beverage brands which seems to be silently but consistently altering the determinants of university undergraduates' preference for beverage brands.

University undergraduates beverage segment appear to be constantly searching for information in order to make informed purchase decisions. Though beverage brands have been described as recession-proof (KPMG, 2012), North-central university undergraduates as a component of Nigeria society are presently witnessing stagflation which have serious potential of modifying to some degree their brand preference criteria; heighten disloyalty, and probably alter purchase patterns. This observation seems likely as consumers, especially university undergraduates, have been implicated with repertoire purchase behavior (Root, Fiorentino, & Dessard, 2014).

Statement of the Problem

Nigerian beverage industry is increasingly witnessing unprecedented expansion of imported chocolate beverage alongside a revolution-like trend in the locally-manufactured brands. Expectedly, heightened competition and consumer mobility appears to be increasing steadily. The campaigns for consumption of made-in-Nigerian campaign by different levels of government seem to be silently but consistently altering brand preference criteria among university undergraduates. Indeed, the primacy and urgency for this research appears doubtless as evidence within the extant literature demonstrates that a clear understanding of the factors affecting brand preference is critical to ensure that branding efforts by the company are synchronized with the needs of local consumers of chocolate beverages (Chimboza & Mutandwa, 2007).

Empirical evidence on effect of brand name on consumer preference is mixed and conflicting. For instance, Tekin, Tiltay and Ayaz (2016) findings revealed positive relationship between brand name and consumers, perception taste and preferences. Bhattacharjee, Chowdhury and Hossain (2012) result indicated significant impact of brand name on consumer preference. Okocha (2012) found that branding was significant in the determination of customer's patronage of malt drinks. Aron and Kenny (2016) found that brand association has significant effect on consumer brand preferences and purchase intentions. Tooraj and Elham (2012) found that the dimensions of brand function have positive effect on the consumer's response. Baseer, Danish, Mirza and Sana (2015) found a practical relation between brand image and teenager consumer buying behaviour. Achmad, Djumilah, Siti and Solimun (2014) study revealed that brand image has a significant role in influencing the purchasing behavior. Baba (2014) found some correlation between a brand and the behavior displayed by consumers with regards to their purchase decisions. Perera and Dissanayake (2013) study found that brand awareness, brand association and brand perceived quality has significant impact female consumers buying decision. Naufal, Muhammad and Mukhamad (2016) perceived quality and brand image directly affects consumer purchase intention. Isik et al (2015) found that Brand name of a product has significant impact on the overall preferences of the consumers. Zhang and Rozelle (2017) found that brand information does influence Chinese consumer's preference for chocolate. On the contrary, Subhani and Osman (2011) found no significant relationship between brand awareness and its consumer/brand loyalty.

The contradicting empirical evidence shows that relationship between brand name and consumer preference is not yet resolved. Also, university undergraduate segment appears under-reported in the mainstream literature regarding the effect of brand name on chocolate beverage preference and none of the studies were carried out among undergraduate students in North Central Nigeria. Overall, it is evident that an important knowledge gap exists currently in the literature which this study seeks to fill. Therefore, this study examined the effect of brand name on consumer preferences for chocolate beverages in north central states.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to determine empirically the effect of brand name on university undergraduates' preference for a particular chocolate beverage in North-central Nigeria. This broad objective will be split into the following specific objectives:

1. To determine the influence of brand awareness on university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage.
2. To determine the influence of brand image on university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage.
3. To determine the influence of brand quality on the university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage.
4. To determine the influence of brand association on university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study enumerated above, the following research questions will be formulated to guide this study.

1. Does brand awareness influence university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage?
2. To what extent does brand image influence university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage?
3. Does brand quality influence university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage?
4. To what extent does brand association influence university undergraduates' preference for a chocolate beverage?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for testing based on the objectives of the study.

- Ho₁: Brand awareness has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.
- Ho₂: Brand image has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.
- Ho₃: Brand quality has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate.
- Ho₄: Brand association has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study comprised of the geographical, unit of analysis, and content scope. The geographical scope is restricted to North central states (Kogi, Nasarawa, Kwara, Niger, Benue, Plateau), Nigeria; the unit of analysis scope will be undergraduates in Federal universities across the six(6) states. In terms of content scope, this is a consumer-based research but restricted to effect of brand name on consumer preference for chocolate beverages. In this study brand

awareness, brand image, brand quality and brand association were employed as the independent variable while university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage was employed as the dependent variable. The major chocolate beverage brands covered in this study include Bournvita from the production line of Cadbury Nigeria Plc, Milo, manufactured by Nestle Nigeria Plc, Ovaltine, produced by Twinning Nigeria, Cowbell Choco, manufactured by Promasidor Nigeria Limited and Horlicks, produced by Glaxosmithkline Consumer Plc.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Brand Name

A brand is a name, picture, plan, image, or blend of those things utilized by advertisers to distinguish its contributions and to separate them from rivalry (Kotler and Keller, 2006). A brand name is an endeavor to force some sort of distinguishing highlight on an item or administration so it is handily perceived by the intended interest group. A brand is frequently connected with a picture; a bunch of assumptions. The objective of a brand is to set an item and additionally benefits separated from others of its sort and impact the buyer to pick the item over comparable items (Lee, 2010). Oddly, if customers don't comprehend the significance of a brand or if the importance implies something negative, it influences the manner in which the individual will see the item. Purchasers abuse brand names to build, keep up, and elevate their character and to encounter passionate delight. Significantly, proof inside the surviving writing upholds the association between brand name and buyer decision (Abdel and Khaled, 2010).

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness alludes to the capacity of potential consumers to perceive the brand while arranging the brand to a particular class (Aaker, 1991). It is accepted that brand mindfulness is one of the principle subjects to focus on in brand value. To second, as indicated by Shimp (2010), from the customer's point, a brand has no value except if consumers is in any event mindful of the brand. The review of brand awareness depends on a continuum where the brand acknowledgment is in the least level and the most elevated level where the named brand is obliging independent wiping out. With respect to the item, it is critical to be perceived and arrive at awareness level among other comparative or indistinguishable things while the potential consumer is settling on buy choices. As per Blackwell et al. (2001), the item should be in the arrangement of mindfulness before the thought stage is being reached. It is accepted that brands with a more significant level of acknowledgment would be almost certain bought than the ones with no acknowledgment. In addition, brand awareness is an underlying objective for new brands. In view of Hoyer (1990), this is a clarification why customer purchases notable brands instead of obscure ones. To expand the differentiation of brand awareness referenced before there is the method of expanding it. As Keller (2003) proposes brand awareness can be expanded through rehashed composition. This implies that item's image personality and attribution to certain class organization will prevail with regards

to accomplishing brand mindfulness on the lookout. Making promotions and including famous people's presentation are accepted to be valuable procedures for expanding brand awareness. The exposure of promoting efforts with famous people has expanded quickly during ongoing many years. It is expected that superstar support could give incredible contribution to the making of item appeal to clients and expanding brand awareness.

Brand Image

Consumers think about certain qualities of an item prior to settling on buying choice. Keller (1993) expressed that the brand image is the view of an item which is an impression of clients' memory in the item. Brand is characterized as an image that can be recollected by general society, which makes a positive brand, significant and simple to recall by individuals (Aaker, 1997). Brand image that was made to make individuals consider everything from the business side, in order to be plainly characterized brand image can profit the organization in the long haul (Cannon, Perreault, and McCarthy, 2009; Morgan and Hunt, 1994). Keller (1993) alludes to the image of the brand as an idea that is expected by the customers because of abstract reasons and their very own feelings. Brand image is likewise alluded to as the customer's view of either the explanation or sane premise or through more feelings towards a particular brand (Cannon, Perreault, and McCarthy, 2009). The fundamental issue of a brand lies not just restricted to the determination of the actual name however is positively a decision of good name could help (Aaker, 1997). Yet, that can make a solid brand name is saliency, the capacity of differentiation (differentiability), brilliance (intensity) and trust that were related with the brand (Wantara, 2008).

Brand perceived quality

The third significant trait of brand equity is perceived quality. As per Aaker (1991), saw quality is the customer's discernment about the general nature of the item. The insight about the item quality is emotional and it is developed by various information on a similar item determination. In light of Kirmani and Zeithaml (1993), while developing brand value chiefs endeavor to impact customer's discernment about quality. By doing this supervisors build up a positive brand image. Seen quality can exhibit better situation on the lookout and make for the customer motivation to purchase while additional cost would not be considered as regrettable factor. As indicated by DeLong et al. (2004), perceived quality can be considered a determinant for brand loyalty and over and again made purchases. Perceived quality could be indicated and arranged into two elements – product quality and service quality. product quality is partitioned into seven measurements, which as accepted by Aaker (1991), may influence customer's insight about the product's quality. In respects with an product, quality dimensions are performance, reliability, conformance with specifications, features, service ability, perfect fit and finish. Then again, service perceived quality could be portrayed by five dimensions, for example, Tangible, competence, responsiveness, empathy and reliability (Aaker, 1991).

Brand Association

The fourth element of brand value is relationship of the brand. As indicated by Aaker (1991), brand association is viewed as a connection between a customer's memory and the brand. Keller (2003) adds that, brand equity is upheld by the customer's relationship towards the brand which makes a particular and special brand image. With respect to items, considered as unmistakable things, the immaterial strengths (for instance, creativity and so on) are remembered for brand association. As indicated by Keller (2003), brand association could be separated into three areas like attributes, benefits and attitudes. Attributes is the class where explicit qualities of the item are appeared. Properties could be arranged into item related and non-item related qualities. product related properties are considered as broad highlights of the item (for example actual make-up of specific great) while non-item related traits are the ones which are considered as bundling, cost and so on Advantages are the second class of the brand association. Ongoing classification could be arranged into practical – The actual benefits, trial – identified with buyers' enthusiastic conduct and Symbolic – how attractive the brand is to the client. Ultimately, the disposition class depicts the general assessment about the brand – how clients feel about the brand in a drawn out viewpoint assessing from negative to good scale (Gabbott and Hogg, 1998). Various brands have different relationship to present and expected customers. As indicated by Aaker (1991), these associations are thought to be a reason for future buys or even as a trigger to draw in faithful clients to the brand. Relationship about the brand can assist with making or improve the worth of the brand to similar level as faithful clients. Buyers, when confronted with numerous brands, can fail to remember one brand over another, however associations got from their recollections can help while they settle on buying choices.

Consumer Preferences

Consumer preference is utilized fundamentally to intend to choose an alternative that has the best expected worth among various choices by the customer to fulfill his/her necessities or wants. Preferences show decisions among impartial or more esteemed choices accessible. The preference of the customer is the consequence of their conduct they show during looking, buying and arranging the products. Consumers preference are characterized as the abstract (individual) tastes, as estimated by utility, of different heaps of products. They license the purchaser to rank these heaps of merchandise as per the degrees of utility they give the buyer. The inclinations are free of pay and costs. Ability to buy goods doesn't decide a consumer's preferences or dislikes. All in all, the shopper has various inclinations over the various blends of products characterized by the arrangement of product packages. Consumer preferences are estimated as far as the degree of satisfaction the buyer gets from burning-through different blends or heaps of merchandise. The buyer's goal is to pick the heap of merchandise which gives the best degree of satisfaction as they the consumer characterize it. However, purchasers are particularly compelled in their decisions. These limitations are characterized by

the customer's pay, and the costs the buyer pays for the merchandise. Customer esteem is estimated as far as the overall utilities among products and these mirror the consumer's preferences (Ubeja and Patel, 2014).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This work is anchored on brand loyalty correlated theory. This theory was proposed by Engel, Blackwell and Kollat (1978). This theory asserts that buyer attributes, shopping design qualities and market structure qualities potentiate customer steadfastness to a particular item. As per this theory, market structure attributes incorporate brand name which houses brand picture, brand association, perceived quality and brand awareness. In view of this theory, they work with attitudinal or personal conduct standards particularly purchaser inclination for a specific item or item classification. They believed that other market structure qualities are value vacillations, accessibility of brands, advancement and managing movement. This theory likewise expresses that customer qualities incorporate age, pay, schooling and other financial and segment factors. Shopping design qualities incorporate store devotion, shopping inclination, amount of products bought, between buy time. Yeboah et al, 2013 and Najafi and Rahmani (2013) have utilized this theory in their investigation.

Proposed Conceptual Framework

Source: Adapted from Engel et al (1978). Consumer behaviour, third edition. Illinois: The Dryden Press.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Brand name and consumer preference has pulled in much empirical consideration. For example, Subhani and Osman (2011) completed an examination on the relationship between brand awareness and consumer/brand reliability for the bundled milk industry in Pakistan. An example of 200 and eighty (280) respondents utilizing bundled milk brands in Karachi was examined. Pearson Chi-square (trial of autonomy) is utilized to test the connection between brand mindfulness measurements and shopper/brand faithfulness measurement. The examination tracked down no critical connection between brand awareness and its consumer/image steadfastness. The investigation showed that brand mindfulness isn't assuming a huge part to affect a ware item like milk to make a rehashed buy, because of arbitrary exchanging buy conduct and low contribution

in purchasing an accommodation item which offers no separation among the brand.

Aron and Kenny (2016) analyzed the impact of brand association on brand preference and purchase intention of youthful South-east Asian buyers. Information assortment was led in the National University of Singapore over a time of five days, during which a sum of 459 useable polls was assembled. Illustrative insights, connection and relapse examination was utilized in investigating the information. The discoveries demonstrate brand inclination and buy aim are impacted by the brand affiliations. Essentially, the discoveries show solid determinants of association and buy expectation are value discernments, picture congruency, sentiments and character.

Tooraj and Elham (2012) analyzed the impacts of brand association on consumer reaction. The examination suggested that ensure, individual recognizable proof, social ID and status will impact the purchaser's readiness to suggest the brand, address a cost premium for it and acknowledge brand expansions. 310 clients of cell phone in Mashhad city in fall and winter of 2010 were examined. Way Analysis and Structural Equation Model (SEM) are utilized in investigating the information. The investigation found that guarantee, individual recognizable proof, social ID and status, the elements of brand work has constructive outcome on the shopper's reaction (Extension, Recommendation, Price Premium). The outcomes got affirm the accommodation of breaking down brand affiliations independently and empower the learning of the brand association that are the most applicable to achieve certain shopper reactions.

Baseer, Danish, Mirza and Sana (2015) inspected the effect of brand image on purchasing behavior among teens. The target of this examination study is to dissect the effect of brand image on young people brand decision, wellspring of data, factors influencing purchasing decision and level of fulfillment. The example of the examination is 300 respondents in which 150 understudies were browsed schools and 150 understudies were chosen from universities of Karachi. Relapse examination and Pearson relationship was utilized in investigating the information. The outcome showed that the fluctuation in purchasing conduct of teens is clarify by the effect of notice on purchasing conduct, commercial's effect on brand picture and brand picture sway on brand dependability. The aftereffects of Pearson relationship shows that young people purchasing conduct is essentially associated with youngster's reliability and with promotion sway on brand picture. The young people purchasing conduct is likewise emphatically and fundamentally related with promotion.

Perera and Dissanayake (2013) inspected the effect of brand awareness; brand perceived quality and brand association quality on female shoppers' buy choice of unfamiliar cosmetics items in Sri Lankan. In the investigation, the connections between each chose brand value component and female buyer buy choice were analyzed alongside theories created. An example of 200 female purchasers was contemplated. Illustrative insights and connection examination was utilized in dissecting the information. Results uncovered that there were critical connections between brand awareness, brand association and brand perceived quality and female purchasers purchasing choice of unfamiliar

cosmetics items and those components were profoundly affecting female buyers purchasing choice of unfamiliar cosmetics items. The investigation likewise found that among the chose brand value determinants, brand mindfulness was the most compelling component towards buy choice with a relationship worth of 0.918.

METHODOLOGY

This research employs descriptive survey design and the target population for the research consists of 45,173 undergraduate students of federal universities across north central states. Taro Yamane formula was used to derive a sample size of 396. Structured questionnaire was employed as the major instrument of data collection. Pearson correlation and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was adopted to analyze the relationship between dependent variables and the independent variables in the model formulated for the study.

The model of the study is developed to reflect whether brand name has effect on consumer preferences for chocolate beverages in North Central states of Nigeria. Thus brand variables such as Brand Image (BI), Brand Quality (BQ), Brand Awareness (BAW), and Brand Association (BAS) have effect on consumer preferences (CP) for Chocolate beverages in North Central States of Nigeria.

$$CP = f(BQ, BAW, BI, BAS)$$

$$CP = a_0 + a_1BQ + a_2BAW + a_3BI + a_4BAS + p$$

Where:

- CP = Consumer Preference
- BQ = Brand Quality
- BAW = Brand Awareness
- BI = Brand Image
- BAS = Brand Association
- P = Error Term
- a = Constant a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 are the coefficients of the independent variables

RESULTS

Correlation Analysis

The Pearson correlation was employed to measure of the strength of a linear association between two variables and to measure the existence or otherwise of multicollinearity in the research model. The result of the correlation test is presented in 1 below.

Table 1 Correlation Matrix

	CP	BAW	BI	BQ	BAS
Consumer Preference	1	.637**	.774**	.615**	.508**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.008	.001	.769	.879
N	372	372	372	372	372

	Pearson	.637**	1	.343**	.031	.259**
Brand	Correlation					
Awareness	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.546	.000
	N	372	372	372	372	372
	Pearson	.774**	.343**	1	.058	.207**
Brand	Correlation					
Image	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.262	.000
	N	372	372	372	372	372
	Pearson	.615**	.031	.058	1	.113*
Brand	Correlation					
Quality	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.546	.262		.029
	N	372	372	372	372	372
	Pearson	.508**	.259**	.207**	.113*	1
Brand	Correlation					
Association	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.029	
	N	372	372	372	372	372

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Table 1 above, brand awareness has a correlation coefficient value of 0.637 with consumer preference which is statistically significant at 5% level. This shows that brand awareness has a very strong positive relationship with university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage. Brand image recorded a correlation coefficient value of 0.774 with consumer preference which is statistically significant at 0.05 levels. This implies that brand image has a very strongly positive relationship with university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Table 1 further indicates that brand quality has a correlation coefficient value of 0.615 with consumer preference at 5% level of significant. This indicates that brand quality has very strong positive relationship with university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage. On a similar note, brand association recorded a correlation coefficient value of 0.508 which is statistically significant at 5% level. This implies that brand association has a strong positive influences university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage. Finally, all the variables used in the study brand awareness, brand image, brand quality and brand association are not perfectly linearly correlated since none of the correlation coefficient value is in excess of 0.8. We therefore conclude that there is no problem of multicollinearity in the model used in this study.

REGRESSION RESULT

Ordinary Least Square regression technique was employed to determine the relationship between the explanatory variables and the dependent variable. The results are presented in table 2, 3 and 4.

Table 2: Summary of the Regression Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.199 ^a	.540	.429	3.085	1.959

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Association, Brand Quality, Brand Image, Brand Awareness

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

Table 3: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	144.034	4	36.009	3.784	.005 ^b
	Residual	3492.127	367	9.515		
	Total	3636.161	371			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Association, Brand Quality, Brand Image, Brand Awareness

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Table 2 shows that R^2 which measures the strength of the influence of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.540. This implies that 54% of the variation in the consumer preference is explained by variations in brand association, brand quality, brand image, and brand awareness. This was supported by adjusted R^2 of 0.429. The Durbin-Watson statistics was employed to check for autocorrelation in the model. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.959 showed that the variables in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications.

The f-statistics value of 3.784 in table 3 above with probability value of 0.005 shows that the independent variables has significant relationship with the dependent. This shows that brand association, brand quality, brand image, and brand awareness can collectively explain the variations in the university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the hypotheses earlier formulated in chapter one are tested using the t-statistics and probability value from the regression result. The result is presented in table 4 below:

Table 4 T-Statistics and Probability Value

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
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	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	16.429	1.840		8.929	.000
Brand Awareness	.124	.071	.197	3.751	.005
1 Brand Image	.159	.058	.151	2.753	.006
Brand Quality	.028	.066	.122	2.426	.006
Brand Association	.053	.061	.166	2.859	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Brand awareness has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Hi: Brand awareness has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Table 4 indicates that brand awareness recorded a t-statistics value of 3.751 with a probability value of 0.005. Base on the t-statistics value which is statistically significant, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. We conclude that brand awareness has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Brand image has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Hi: Brand image has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Brand image recorded a t-statistics value of 2.753 and a probability value 0.006. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that brand image has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Brand quality has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate.

Hi: Brand quality has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate.

Table 4 indicates that brand quality recorded a t-statistics value of 2.426 with a probability value of 0.006 which is statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that brand quality has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate.

Test of Hypothesis Four

Ho₄: Brand Association has no significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Hi: Brand Association has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

Brand Association recorded a t-statistics value of 2.859 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore, we reject

the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that brand Association has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the effect of brand name on undergraduate preference for chocolate beverage in North Central Nigeria. Data were sourced from undergraduates of six universities in the region. The data generated were analyzed and the following were observed. The study found that brand awareness has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. This finding collaborates the finding of Perera et al (2013) that brand awareness is the most influential element towards purchase decision. It also tallies with the findings of Naufal et al (2016) that brand awareness affects consumer purchase intention. This implies that university undergraduates awareness of chocolate beverage influence their preference for the products.

The result also revealed that brand image has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. This agrees with the findings of Baseer et al (2015) that brand image has a significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour. It also agrees with the findings of Achmad et al (2014) that that brand image has a significant role in influencing the purchasing behavior. This implies that brand image Chocolate brand relevant and easy to be remembered by undergraduates studied. Hence, university undergraduates' perception of chocolate beverages influences their preference for the product.

The findings further showed that brand quality has a significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate North Central Nigeria. This tally with the findings of Erfan et al (2013) that the relationship between brand image and brand equity is mediated by perceived quality. It is also in line with the findings of Naufal et al (2016) that perceived quality significantly affects consumer purchase intention. This implies that the overall quality of the studied chocolate products influences the university undergraduate's choice of the products. They choose one beverage product over another based on the quality of the brand.

Finally, brand association was found to have significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. This is in line with the findings of Aron et al (2016) that brand preference and purchase intention are influenced by the brand associations. It also agrees with the findings of Tooraj et al (2012) that brand association has positive effect on consumer response. This implies that when university undergraduates are faced with many chocolate beverage brands, the associations derived from their memories about the product influences their preference for a particular Chocolate brand.

CONCLUSION

This work examined the effect of brand name on undergraduate preference for chocolate beverage in North Central Nigeria. Data were sourced from undergraduates of six universities in the region. The data generated were analyzed and the following were observed. The study found that brand awareness has a positive significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. The result also revealed that brand image has a positive significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. The findings further showed that brand quality has a positive significant effect on university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate North Central Nigeria. Finally, brand association was found to have significant positive effect on university undergraduates' preference for chocolate beverage North Central Nigeria. Base on the foregoing, the study concludes that brand name has significant positive effect university undergraduates' preference for beverage chocolate North Central Nigeria.

The study recommends that organizations could strategically plan to allocate budget over different branding activities, giving preference & priority to the more influencing brand awareness. Also the marketers can use more promotional tools in order to increase the awareness level of products. Also, organizations and marketers should use effective promotional tools to create strong brand awareness within customers' minds. Also, organization should improve the quality of products in order to create loyal customers towards their brands. Also organization should provide a proper level of ingredient quality and functional quality in order to enhance consumer preference.

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